

Postcolonial Arab Science-Fiction Resistance through (Dis)-Appearance: Reclaiming Space and Memory in *The Book of Disappearance* by Ibtissam Azem

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Abstract

This research paper presents a thorough textual analysis of the postcolonial concepts of resistance, identity, memory, absence, and space in the novel *The Book of Disappearance* written by Azem Ibtissam. The purpose of this research is to scrutinize and analyze the binaries appearance and disappearance set in a dystopian geopolitical space where dynamics of power relations distort etymologies and falsify the politics of mention. It will also focus on the pertinent use of science fiction and magical realism through the absence of chronology and the presence of flashbacks as narratological vehicles that facilitate the movement beyond the limits of the concepts of time, reality, and truth, as well as third and first-person narration in an omnipresent fashion. This textual analysis will shed further light on depersonalization and detachment associated with the lived experiences of the colonized, what makes their subjective realities different from those of the colonizer, and impacts their identities providing them with an inchoate fluidity and ambivalence. The ongoing conflict between Palestine and Israel and the occurring clash of civilization that has been present and persistent since the Nakba provides fertile grounds for postcolonial perusal and interpretation. The results of this analysis pertain to the fact that the concepts of space, memory, truth, belonging, identity, shape and redefine mainstream history. This latter has always been written by a biased hegemony and subjectively alter the collective unconscious of differing peoples.

Key words: post-colonial; resistance; (dis)appearance; space; memory; history

1. Introduction

Being known as the bride of Palestine and one of its oldest cities, Jaffa has always been at the center of many Palestinian literary works¹. *The Book of Disappearance* is nothing but another novel about and for Jaffa. Yet, although it shares many aspects with the previously written Palestinian novels about this city, it still offers an exceptional fictional perspective that the literary genre adopted allows. The space of Jaffa in this novel is not only disturbed by the Israeli settlement but also by a dystopian disappearance of Palestinians from the city. For the first time, Jaffa is present in a Palestinian novel without the Jaffans and their absence from this space, which must be historically considered a victory for the settlers, is not but a source of their anguish.

This paper openly argues that this novel is about the story of Jaffa; not that of Alaa or his Tata, and not that of Ariel and his colonial culture. Yet, Jaffa is not a single city in this literary work but rather multiple cities. From the very beginning of the novel, this idea is explicitly revealed through Alaa's statement to his dead grandmother:

Your Jaffa resembles mine. But it is not the same. Two cities impersonating each other. You carved your names in my city, so I feel like I am a returnee from history. Always tired, roaming my own life like a ghost. Yes, I am a ghost who lives in your city. You, too, are a ghost, living in my city. And we call both cities Jaffa.²

Alaa's claim of the plurality of the city and the interconnected complex ties between these different Jaffas encapsulate the significance of this space and its centrality to the novel and to this paper. Before the compulsory exodus of thousands of Palestinians in 1948, Jaffa was the commercial, industrial, and cultural capital of Palestine³. It symbolized Arab affluence that was disastrously aborted by the settlement. This pivotal position is indeed what makes it an unhealed wound in the hearts and collective memory of Palestinians⁴. Consequently, comparing and contrasting the Jaffa before and after 1948 is

inscribed not only in literature but also in the Palestinian popular culture. By overly praising the old Jaffa and mourning the present one, Palestinians display excessive feelings of nostalgia that make them crave going back to the past and live in the old Jaffa. This longing is also experienced by younger generations who had never physically lived through that prosperous era, but who are able to relive it through the older generations.

Indeed, this explains the over-attachment of Alaa to his *Tata* and her persisting presence through his diaries and the text. It is not a bond with the person as much as it is a tenacious tie with her representation of the socio-political space of Jaffa, as he states; “I told you once that, with you, I felt that I was living the world of your Jaffa before ‘that year’”⁵. However, this attitude adopted by Alaa is refused by his grandmother who believes that “Jaffa will always be Jaffa”⁶. She thinks that considering the fact that Jaffa has changed into another Jaffa is itself an act of surrender. This pluralism that is both suggested by Alaa and this paper degrades Jaffa according to the grandmother.

The question that emerges here is would a city really remain the same even after colonization? Or would it rather be its paralleled version that will be able to survive in the collective memory and imaginary? An early answer that we provide to these two questions is: no. Neither will the city be the same in reality nor will it remain authentic even in imagination and memory. Yet, the strong emotional bond that Jaffians have with their city forces them to keep reliving its glorious memories and never allow the settler to erase the truthful memory of the place. Actually, along with space, the concepts of truth and collective memory reign strongly as one of the most important themes of the novel. Azem makes sure to highlight the fact that despite the continuous dire efforts of the colonizer to expunge and erase the colonized memory and truthful sense of identity, this latter persists and continues to forcefully and painfully remember through detailed routines within the Jaffan spatial constructs.

2. A Tale of Two Cities: Jaffa and Jafa

Dispute over preserving and destroying the memory of the city is present all throughout the novel as it is projected through the crisis of naming. Public spaces' naming is actually an issue that attracts the attention of many postmodern debates with political ends; including feminism, blackism, and postcolonialism. Names of streets all around the world are being revisited in an attempt to promote political correctness. The case in Palestine was reversed because, in the second half of the twentieth century, the original Arab names of streets were replaced by Hebrew-Jewish names as Alaa states "I used to repeat whenever I went through Rayzal Street, the name that had occupied Iskandar Awad Street"⁷. Renaming the streets of Jaffa is part of the settler's agenda to erase the Palestinian identity; as it is considered an outspoken form of symbolic violence against its culture. In fact, according to Ernesto Laclau, names are considered "performative catalysts for popular identities"⁸, and by replacing them either with Hebrew names or numbers they perform a kind of soft power that makes original Palestinian streets unrecognizable.

For this reason, remembering is a very important theme in Palestinian literature in general and in this novel specifically. The second enemy after the Zionists is forgetfulness. To fight this enemy, not only Palestinians are pushed to remember, but Jaffa is also forced to remember its citizens, history, and legacy. The personification of the city is a result of the strong emotional involvement of its citizens, as it is the catalyzer of a soft form of resistance. Furthermore, there is an established metaphor of Jaffa as a woman/mother who has a heart that is overwhelmed by melancholy, a body agonized by weapons, and a memory that, although forced into dissociative amnesia, still remembers⁹. However, remembrance is not always an act of resistance when it includes endless insights into one's own vulnerability.

Death is an unconditional element in Jaffa's memory. The book opens with the grandmother's death. This might be interpreted in two ways. First, we can assume

that the death of the grandmother symbolizes the end of the old Jaffa. Second, death might refer to the eternal stay of the grandmother in Jaffa's soil. Yet, natural death is not the weakest point in Jaffa's memory but is rather death caused by annihilation and homicides. As Alaa states; "Should I tread lightly? Was I walking over the corpses of those who had passed through, and who were decimated in the nakba? ... When I walk in Palestine I feel that I am walking on corpses"¹⁰. After the arrival of the settlers, death has dominated the space of Jaffa which made the city unbearable to live in.

Jaffa is at the same time the long-loved and the hated, the desired and unsought. These ambivalent feelings torment Alaa as they push him to interrogate his faithful commitment to the city. The fact that he lives in Tel Aviv also aggravates his identity crisis as he lives in Rothschild Boulevard just because he refuses to live in Ghettos in his own country¹¹. The noticeable socioeconomic differences between Tel Aviv and Jaffa, where so many Arabs are still living, also enrage Alaa.

Becoming a stranger in one's homeland is what made leaving less difficult for a vast category of Palestinians who could have stayed. Alaa's grandfather preferred real exile rather than exile in Palestine. This partial massive departure of Palestinians has allowed the settler to destruct the authenticity of the space under the pretext of modernization. But, what if not even one Palestinian stays in Palestine? Would this finally make the dream of the settlers come true?

The political dispute over owning space was settled by Azem in favor of the Israelis. However, the dominance of the space in the shades of an unexplained, illogical, and even abnormal disappearance of Palestinians cannot be celebrated. Yet, a large number of Israelis still celebrated it. The conflicting opinions over the reason behind this disappearance raised tension in the already strained colonized space. Being nowhere is a hollow inference that is beyond the bounds of logic as Ariel states that "one still has to be somewhere"¹². Reclaiming space through this

abnormal out-of-placeness is only reached through the narrative structure that magical realism provides.

As a matter of fact, magical realism allows postcolonial authors a margin of freedom to subvert the diverse discourses of power that cannot be found in any other genre. According to Bakhtin, magical realism “provides a means to fill in the gaps of cultural representation in a postcolonial context by recuperating the fragments and voices of forgotten or subsumed histories from the point of view of the colonized”¹³. This gap is used by the author to subordinate the settlers to noticing, thinking, and even worrying about the Palestinians’ absence. Both the grandmother’s and Alaa’s Jaffas are deconstructed and a new Jaffa, where Palestinians are completely dismissed, is reconstructed. This imaginative alternative reconstruction of Jaffa as a Palestinians-free space where Israelis become more anxious also delineates the fact that the absence of the victim can also cause trauma to the subjugator.

It is certain that the mysteriousness involved in this disappearance is the aspect that intensified the feeling of angst, but it is also the dialectic of the master and slave that subconsciously increased worries. Reactions to the disappearance varied from one person to another and from one political view to another. Yet, the colonial ambitions that pushed Palestinians into physical and metaphorical homelessness resurfaced. In less than two days, the “abandoned” Palestinian houses became the subject of a good deal of real estate. Among the people who cherished this opportunity was Ariel’s mother who expressed her excitement towards moving to Jaffa as she has been “eyeing a house on Abbas Street”¹⁴ for a long time. This fast will to own the deserted houses puts into question the resisting aspect of absence and shows that houses are as central to this work as are the two different, yet similar, cities of Jaffa and Jafa.

3. The Haunting of Alaa's House: The house as a Metaphor

A house is not only a place that provides people with shelter and helps them develop their own sense of home, it is a space that represents the boundary between the private-public and the public-public. In this section, we will follow the Bergsonian tradition of “reading the house”. Nevertheless, the ideologically loaded context in which we will be reading the house coerces us to focus on the political rather than the poetic. In his pivotal work “Poetics of Space”, Bergson suggests that houses are more than just the limits that divide the public and domestic spheres. They can be considered the world itself as he believes that houses are “our first universe, a real cosmos in every sense of the word”¹⁵. Consequently, transgressing the borders of someone's house, especially without their permission, can automatically be considered a brutal invasion of someone's intimate world.

Historically, the Israeli settlement did not only invade Palestinian houses and took them by force, but they also bombarded and demolished them¹⁶. In the novel, the grandmother's family house collapsed because of a bombing, and took away all its inhabitants, as she describes it; “the building died, and they (her family) died with it”¹⁷. Replacing collapsing with dying, which equally refers to both the family and the house, shows that her house was not just a set of soulless bricks, but actually part of her family.

This physical pulverization was added to the allegorical one when all Palestinian houses were disowned and were given to the Jewish people who were arriving from the four quarters of the world. On one hand, and in the fictive tense of this novel, the government's spontaneous response to the disappearance of Palestinians by taking away their houses is a historically and politically anticipated action. On the other, the way Ariel allowed himself into Alaa's house with no permission might be considered the shocking element in the novel. At the beginning of chapter fifteen, it is made clear that Alaa and Ariel “exchanged spare keys (just) in case one of them lost his”¹⁸. That is, Ariel does not have the right to

enter Alaa's house, let alone go through his personal belongings and make himself at home. However, abusing intimacy and transgressing confidence is actually not unfamiliar to the character of Ariel whose occupation was to read and translate letters that circulate between Palestinians. Thus, entering into a house that is not his own revived the intrusiveness that he tried to hide with the pretext of being steered only by his attempt to understand what happened.

The fact that Ariel could invade Alaa's intimate geopolitical space without any difficulties or problems pushes us to question the efficiency of the aspect of absence as a postcolonial answer back to the settlement. However, the author added rather disturbing elements that cut short Ariel's feelings of easiness during the moments of transgression. Right after opening the door, Ariel was faced with "the (strong) aroma of the cardamom (that) Alaa used to put in his coffee"¹⁹. Actually, it is possible to find cardamom mentioned in every Palestinian literary work at least once. In his prose poem "Memory for Forgetfulness", Darwish refers to this herb as a geographical direction towards a Palestinian house. He says,

Walk out the door and go left, then turn right. Go twenty meters, then turn left for thirty and take another right. There you'll find a huge chinaberry, a lone tree that will lead you to a small courtyard. Cross it **and follow the aroma of cardamom** to this building's entrance, like a shark chasing the smell of blood.²⁰

The intersection between geographical space and smells is also manifested through this novel. Coffee with cardamom is one of the national labels of Palestine. It capsulizes the fragments of the Palestinian identity that the settler tries to eradicate. The fact that Ariel was hit by this smell once he entered proposes that Alaa's display of out-of-placeness does not imply his out-of-spaceness. Despite Alaa's virtual absence, Ariel finds himself still unable to fully occupy his house.

This disturbance becomes even more interesting when a painting hanging on the wall becomes the source of an apparent psychological agitation for Ariel. By adding to the setting of the living room a painting that displays a Palestinian,

Azem aims to intensify the character's distress. In fact, it is not the painting of a Palestinian per se that causes Ariel a sudden perturbation, but it is rather one single part of this genderless person's body; their eyes. Taking this point into consideration, we can assume that this painting is not there only to occupy space but also to watch it, as the unknown omniscient narrator explains; "the veiled person's eyes in the painting on the wall across from him glistened as they gazed at him. It was strange, he thought, that a painting could unsettle him"²¹.

In the shades of the magical absence of Alaa from his own apartment and the actual absence of his grandmother, this painting still performs existence and occupancy of the space. This small artistic visual addition to the house's furniture successfully subverts the relations of power between the absent and the present. This hung gaze can also be compared to the most famous gaze in the history of modern literature in Orwell's 1948;

...the poster with the enormous face gazed from the wall. It was one of those pictures which are so contrived that the eyes follow you about when you move. BIG BROTHER IS WATCHING YOU, the caption beneath it ran.²²

Without the need for any caption, Azem's painting openly claims that PALESTINIANS ARE WATCHING YOU. This overly present absence calls into question the truthfulness of the Palestinians' disappearance. Hence, to what extent did Palestinians disappear? And did they appear through disappearing? This appearance/(dis)-appearance paradox eludes the reader's enumeration of the magical elements in the novel.

Apart from the unexplained absence from both the city (public) and the houses (private), the novel gives the delusion that it also engages with haunting and ghosts. Previously deserted houses are represented through Alaa's perspective as haunted. He says: "I pass by the old city houses overlooking the sea... Are they haunted? I want to believe that the spirits of those who used to live in them are still there seeking comfort"²³. A haunted space is by force an occupied space.

Thus, the Palestinian houses, including Alaa's, are not as free as Israelis perceive them. Indeed, the materialistic elements of the Palestinian identity that are highlighted while describing Alaa's apartment are nothing but a few examples among the thousands of things that will be found in other houses. Ghosts of the Palestinian culture will haunt these houses not only through removable furniture, but also through the cement and bricks, and simply through the land on which they are built. In this novel, Alaa's house stands as a metaphor for Palestine. The closure of the text with a passage in which Ariel changed the door lock defines the point where the magical dimension of the novel stops and the realist one begins.

4. The Psychopathology of Everyday Truth

"I didn't shed any tears. Perhaps I had yet to comprehend what had happened. Or maybe I didn't want to believe that she had died"²⁴.

These were the thoughts running through Alaa's mind after the sudden passing of his grandmother. What first started as the probability of an old demented lady's disappearance culminated in her death in her favorite spot near the Jaffan beach. This pertains to the elusiveness of truth and the fact that matters are never as clear-cut as they seem. The frantic distraught and overwrought behavior of Alaa's mother at the beginning of the novel in reaction to the disappearance of her mother foreshadows the agitation in the Israeli behavioral framework on the social and the political fronts once the sudden realization that all Palestinians have disappeared sets. Nevertheless, what represents an act of worry from the former is actually an act of triumph to the latter.

Truth is also symbolized when it comes to the politics of mention. As previously stated, space is one of the most important pawns when it comes to dominion and the establishment of specific power relations. This means that abolishing names provides space with a new fake identity through the pathological act of renaming. Thus, the way space is altered in the novel, where Palestinian street names become

numerals and Hebrew, showcases the distortion of truth within a colonial setting where representations are made to be biased towards the subjugators. In other words, etymology always favors the ever-changing power structures that make appearance grow into becoming disappearance and eventually changes the truth around mainstream history by making it adhere to pure dogmatism and mere subjective interpretations that feed into Grand Narratives.

When Alaa addresses his grandmother while talking about his manic hysterical great-grandfather he relates: "When you told him he was at home, he accused you of lying"²⁵. Lying and equivocating seem to be some of the main themes that Azem focused on in this novel. To put it differently, Alaa's demented great-grandfather can be a metaphor for a shifting and a fleeting discourse that started to squander its authenticity and that eventually and forcefully succumbed to the bias of power relations which results in psychological confusion and physical disorientation when it comes to the concept of home.

In the same vein of etymological lies and dialectal disillusionment that were adopted in order to cover the truth, crimes against humanity committed by the Israeli occupation against the Palestinian colonized are seldom honestly mentioned or scrutinized through the eyes of the media and the press as mentioned in Human Rights Watch's article "A Threshold Crossed - Israeli Authorities and the Crimes of Apartheid and Persecution". The atrocities of murder, genocide, ethnic cleansing, bombings, physical and metaphorical rape, and the expunging of culture, history, and customs are disregarded truths that are only present and persistent within the lived experiences of the sufferers. This out of sight out of mind representation overlooks the colonized people who get their own identities tortured and brainwashed out of them as the excerpt clearly demonstrates: "They threw him out on the street after keeping him in prison for six months. No one knew where he was. He came back a mad man. I don't know what they did to him"²⁶. This highlights the fact that for the colonizer, the surest way to achieve complete forgetfulness is to go through mania and madness.

Consequently, the fragmentation and displacement of truth are depicted throughout the novel in the facts that the politics of mention are governed by hegemony which stresses the multiplicity in naming Tel Aviv based on personal and subjective lived experiences, and that, once it was sure that the Palestinians have actually disappeared, there is a battle of dogmatic, heroic, ecstatic, elevated supremacy, and false hope discourses from the part of the Israeli government that claims victory without even being sure of what is really going on. This pertains to what Alaa mentioned in regard to the institutionalized discourses learned in schools in contrast to the subaltern discourses that stem from lived experiences what recalls Ngugi Wa Thiong'o's notion of the cultural bomb in his essay "Decolonizing the Mind".

Through a discourse of Israel's disillusionment of righteousness of it being the "only democracy in the middle east", there is a nod to the White Man's Burden concept that was used as a historical rationalization and justification of imperialism throughout various empires. Through the unfolding of her novel, Azem attests that these discourses of heroism, valor, and prowess are what veils and disregards the truth surrounding the lived experiences of the colonized and how their small narratives are needed in order to fashion an alternative history.

5. Thus Spoke Collective Memory

It is a known fact that individual long-term memory becomes unreliable with passing time. The same can be said for the collective memories of various peoples throughout the ages. As a consequence, when these memories falter, clash, and become subjective, conflicts arise. Therefore, even if shared memory is able to transcend the temporal and spatial circumstances of colonization as seen through Alaa's grandmother, there is an undeniable trickiness and difficulty when it comes to memory and remembrance. In his foreword "Remembering Fanon: Self, Psyche and the Colonial Condition" of Frantz Fanon's book *Black Skin, White Masks*, Homi Bhabha defines this remembrance as being a painful re-membering that

helps the colonized make sense and work through the traumas of the past and the present.

In addition, since the politics of mention and the concealment of etymologies work only through creating deep holes, prolonged gaps, and persistent breaks in the psyche as well as the collective memory of the colonized people, changes in names entirely refashion and alter their identity, belonging, and history. In other words, this memorabilia and nostalgic feelings associated with remembrance have a crucial effect on the collective unconscious of the subjugated. For this, Alaa writes "The images of multitudes of people escaping in terror are always on my mind"²⁷. This means that the wars crimes and the past horrors of the Nakba are persistent within the minds and the psyches of the Palestinians no matter how young they are. They are all vividly aware of what has befallen them making the reality of that memory always creeping upon them around every corner.

Regardless of the strong and powerful effect of collective memory despite the abundance of forced altering and misrepresenting discourses, this act of remembering is always associated with pain, suffering, nostalgia, and sadness. In this way, memory becomes synonymous with loss, anguish, and heartache, making it a burden too heavy to carry. This is why Azem shows that dementia is the optimal solution for this arduous and harrowing collective memory.

On another flow of thought, Palestinians started experiencing a clash of civilization as a cause of imperialism, capitalism, and globalization. As a result, collectivist communities became more and more individualistic what created a conflict of generations when it came to the questions of identity and belonging. Consequently, and in order to circumvent this generational gap, music and language were used so as to evoke fond memories of belonging, kinship, and remembrance. This makes writing and memory interconnected and intertwined as practices of resistance by representing the last hope of appearing and being remembered.

Another thing worth mentioning is the presence of Michel Foucault's concept of the strategy of containment, from his book *History of Madness*, in the novel. To elaborate, since memory is forced to become part of the prevailing hegemony and ideological discursive practices of the colonizer forming a lie of whiteness, colonized victims of imprisonment and torture are kept alive in order for them to be able to tell their stories and spread fear, terror, and panic to the other prospect victims who might consider retaliation and resistance. These dreadful war tactics have a lasting impact on the hybrid and ambivalent gray collective memory of the colonized.

6. Conclusion

This novel is a fictional staging of the geopolitical chaos that overbears the Palestinian context. The dispute over who owns space and who holds truth continues even if the narrative time stops. This study has investigated the geopolitical dimension of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict without marginalizing the historical part of it that summons the debate of memory. In fact, this novel does not take remembering only as a theme but it is rather a postcolonial mechanism to answer back to western discourses. It is itself an alternative memory that is refreshed through the use of magical realism. The interplay between disappearance (magical) and appearance (realism) put into question the truthfulness of the space's memory. All throughout the novel, we find an interconnection between absence and presence as there is appearance within the word (dis)-appearance. At a certain level, absence becomes a phenomenal possibility that is challenged by the incorporeal presence. In this way, this novel has successfully recuperated space and memory through the violence of absence.

Endnotes

[1] Either with Anouar Ahmad's *Yafa Makes the Morning Coffee*, Kheiri Aboujenin's *Stories about Jaffa* or Moujahid Mourdawi's *Jaffa's Oranges and Damacus' Jasmine*, Jaffa as a socio-

political space has been always the source of a historical agony for Palestinians. Even with the slight changes in perspectives that separate these texts, as some of the authors prefer to remember the happy side of Jaffa while others choose to focus on how horrendous it has become, these texts like Azem's are all characterized by excessive feelings of nostalgia.

[2] Ibtisām 'Āzim. *The Book of Disappearance: A Novel*. Translated by Sinān Anṭūn, Syracuse University Press, 2019. p. 17.

[3] Itamar Radai. *Palestinians in Jerusalem and Jaffa, 1948: A Tale of Two Cities*. Routledge, 2017. p. 182.

[4] Ibid. p. 126.

[5] Ibtisām 'Āzim. *The Book of Disappearance: A Novel*. Translated by Sinān Anṭūn, Syracuse University Press, 2019. p. 66.

[6] Ibid. p. 67.

[7] Ibid. p. 66.

[8] Lawrence D. Berg, Jani Vuolteenaho. *Critical Toponymies: The Contested Politics of Place Naming*. Routledge, 2017.

[9] Ibtisām 'Āzim. *The Book of Disappearance: A Novel*. Translated by Sinān Anṭūn, Syracuse University Press, 2019. pp. 61-97.

[10] Ibid. p. 59.

[11] Ibid. p. 86.

[12] Ibid. p. 73.

[13] Maggie Ann Bowers. *Magical Realism*. Routledge, 2018. p. 96.

[14] Ibtisām 'Āzim. *The Book of Disappearance: A Novel*. Translated by Sinān Anṭūn, Syracuse University Press, 2019. p. 143.

[15] Gaston Bachelard. *The Poetics of Space*. Penguin Books, 2014. p. 4.

[16] Itamar Radai. *Palestinians in Jerusalem and Jaffa, 1948: A Tale of Two Cities*. Routledge, 2017. p. 66.

[17] Ibtisām 'Āzim. *The Book of Disappearance: A Novel*. Translated by Sinān Anṭūn, Syracuse University Press, 2019. p. 14.

[18] Ibid. p. 56.

[19] Ibid. p. 64.

[20] Ibid. p. 72.

[21] Ibid. p. 70.

[22] George Orwell. *1984*. Signet Classic, 1950. p. 3.

[23] Ibtisām 'Āzim. *The Book of Disappearance: A Novel*. Translated by Sinān Anṭūn, Syracuse University Press, 2019. p. 82.

[24] Ibid. p. 10.

[25] Ibid. p. 19.

[26] Ibid. p. 25.

[27] Ibid. p. 59.

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